

1 Beyond the Surface: Coupling Water Permeability Assessments to X-ray Micro-Computed
2 Tomography for Evaluation of Self-Healing on Lime-based Mortars

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4 Franco Grosso Giordano^{1,4,*}, Dulce Valdez Madrid², Laurenz Schröer², Nico Boon¹, Veerle
5 Cnudde^{2,3}, Nele De Belie⁴

6
7 ¹ Ghent University, Center for Microbial Ecology and Technology (CMET), Coupure Links 653, B-
8 9000 Ghent, Belgium

9 ² Ghent University, Dept. Geology, Krijgslaan 281/Building S8, B-9000, Ghent, Belgium

10 ³ Utrecht University, Dept. of Earth Sciences, Princetonlaan 8a, 3584, Utrecht, Netherlands

11 ⁴ Ghent University, Magnel-Vandepitte Laboratory, Dept. of Structural Engineering and Building
12 Materials, Technologiepark Zwijnaarde 60, B-9052, Ghent, Belgium

13 * Corresponding author: franco.grossogiordano@ugent.be

14 **Abstract**

15 Self-healing, a promising solution to cementitious structures' main problem – cracking, involves complex
16 dynamics influenced by factors like crack type, size, and binder material. Existing tests lack a
17 comprehensive approach to describe it. This study coupled the results of X-ray micro-computed
18 tomography (micro-CT) to water flow tests and optical microscopy to obtain 3D crack volume analysis,
19 water permeability, and crack widths, respectively. Three binder formulations - a pure cement, a 50% lime
20 – 50% cement and a 33% lime - 67 % metakaolin mix - were selected to test the method's accuracy across
21 different mortars. On average, pure cement samples exhibited the best healing efficiency in all tests, albeit
22 not significantly. Interestingly, neither water flow nor microscopy measurements could be correlated to
23 crack volume changes, suggesting different aspects of self-healing were captured. Micro-CT analysis
24 provided clarification, revealing that self-healing predominately occurred at the surface. Additionally, the
25 precipitation of self-healing products at the pore-crack interface led to certain pores becoming
26 disconnected from the original crack. Therefore, the measured volume change of the crack appeared to
27 be larger than the actual precipitation of healing products. Given the different limitations encountered on
28 all tests, the use of coupled tests is encouraged for future studies.

29 **Keywords**

30 Self-healing, Lime-based, Mortar, X-ray micro-computed tomography (micro-CT), Material
31 characterization

32 **1. Introduction**

33 Self-healing of cementitious materials has seen an exponential growth as a research topic over the last 20
34 years [1–3]. This interest has risen with the need of decarbonization of the cement industry and the need
35 for longer lasting cementitious materials with lower carbon footprints. Multiple reviews exist that explore
36 the modifications that can promote self-healing, such as bacterial additives [4], microcapsules [5],
37 crystalline admixtures [6] and superabsorbent polymers (SAPs) [7]. Despite that cementitious materials
38 are ubiquitous to the construction industry, new alternatives are also being explored such as geopolymers
39 [8] and other lesser studied binder types, including lime-based materials [9,10].

40 Previous work on self-healing has demonstrated that the capacity of autogenous healing of any material
41 is tied to a variety of parameters that influence the progress of healing such as crack width, crack

42 geometry, rugosity and binder composition. Thus, it is necessary to have a comprehensive understanding
43 of these parameters. Usually, single techniques do not fully illustrate the whole process of healing. 2D
44 techniques such as optical microscopy do not provide insights into the extent of healing through a whole
45 crack. To study the inside of a specimen then, often a destructive approach is required, but this is not
46 desired if multiple testing stages are needed. Due to the limitations of optical microscopy, durability tests
47 that can provide quantification of the healing progress have been developed. These generally include
48 different types of permeability tests and tests of regain in mechanical properties [2,11]. However,
49 durability tests cannot offer descriptive assessments of the healing occurring within the specimens. This
50 information is nonetheless essential to be able to discern the effectiveness of healing, such as where the
51 formation of healing products is happening and to what extent.

52 X-ray micro-computed tomography (micro-CT) [12,13] has been hailed as a promising technique for the
53 study of self-healing due to its capacity to overcome the limitations stated above, while at the same time
54 it is capable of performing both qualitative and quantitative assessments in a non-destructive manner.
55 Snoeck et al. [14], used it to study the capacity of SAPs to improve self-healing in cement mortars and
56 could quantify the amount of healing products generated by the addition of SAPs. They also showed that
57 this precipitation of healing products extended to the pore network. Van Stappen et al. [15], then
58 demonstrated that micro-CT offers a tool to study the distribution and debonding of microcapsules used
59 for self-healing. They argued that intrusive techniques such as optical or electron microscopy can lead to
60 rupture of the microcapsules and indications of healing when there is none. Similarly, Sidiq et al. [16]
61 studied different concentrations of microcapsules and their effect on the healing of a crack. Despite that
62 the addition of larger amounts of microcapsules led to better healing, micro-CT allowed them to confirm
63 that extra additions also hindered bond strength of the matrix with aggregates as the microcapsules
64 reduced hydration. Kontiza et al. [17] also studied microcapsules in cementitious materials although they
65 used micro-CT merely to determine whether their production technique resulted in successful embedding
66 of the microcapsules. Meanwhile, Fan and Li [18] explored the addition of fly-ash to Portland cement, and
67 used micro-CT to study the progress of self-healing on multiple time points and cracks in the same sample.
68 Still, limitations were encountered in these works particularly when it comes to the resolution of the
69 images of the samples. For these reasons, Wang et al. [19], who used micro-CT to study bacterial additives
70 for self-healing, stressed the need to perform micro-CT analysis together with other techniques such as
71 electron microscopy.

72 It is necessary to study self-healing dynamics through a more holistic approach in which multiple
73 techniques are combined. Although different testing methods are used in previous work, these have
74 always been applied on different test series due to the ease of managing samples, the destructive nature
75 of the testing techniques and shape and size requirements for some techniques. Coupled experiments
76 that demonstrate the quantitative and qualitative effect of the healing processes on a single sample are
77 not common due to their technical complications. Few studies, like that of Fukuda et al. [20], have
78 corroborated whether micro-CT was in good agreement with real observations in the same sample.
79 Fukuda et al. [20] used Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) to study a region on the surface of the sample
80 and concluded that they got more robust results that would be hard to achieve if they had relied on the
81 preparation of multiple specimens that compromise reproducibility.

82 Here, the first study is performed to evaluate self-healing by coupling results of microscopy, water
83 permeability tests and micro-CT obtained on the same specimen. Whereas microscopy and water
84 permeability are commonly used techniques to assess self-healing, micro-CT is less used. Nevertheless,
85 the former techniques cannot provide insight into what is occurring within samples. As such, the aim of
86 this work was to use micro-CT scans that visualized the whole crack before and after healing, to study how

87 microscopy and water flow test reflect changes to the internal structure. At the same time, this is applied
 88 on standard-sized specimens, which are more representative of healing dynamics than smaller sized
 89 specimens previously used in most self-healing research using micro-CT. Three mortar mixes of varying
 90 strengths were chosen to evaluate the effectiveness of the method as a universally applicable test in a
 91 range of self-healing materials. Two different lime-based formulations, a 50% lime – 50% cement and a
 92 33% lime - 67 % metakaolin mixture were tested and compared to a cement mixture. The healing
 93 efficiencies obtained in each test were calculated and three samples were chosen for an in-depth
 94 characterization using the micro-CT scans. Furthermore, to our current knowledge this is the first time
 95 self-healing has been reported in a lime-pozzolanic mixture and full crack dynamics are discussed for a
 96 lime-based mortar, which remains a largely understudied material when compared to cement-based
 97 mortars.

98 2. Materials and methods

99 1.1. Materials

100 1.1.1. Mix design

101 Three mortar formulations were designed of cement CEM II A/L 32.5R (Tarmac, United Kingdom),
 102 hydrated lime CL 90-S (Lhoist, Belgium) and metakaolin Metapor (Poraver, Germany). These were a pure
 103 cement binder (C100L0), a 50-50 by volume cement-lime mixture (C50L50) and a 33-67 by volume
 104 metakaolin-lime mixture (M33L67), with a binder-to-aggregate ratio of 1:3 by volume. The bulk densities
 105 of cement, lime and metakaolin were 964 kg/m³, 405 kg/m³ and 296 kg/m³, respectively. The water-to-
 106 binder (w/b) ratio was determined in accordance with EN 1015-2, to reach a flow of 175 ± 10 mm (Table
 107 1). The chemical composition and particle sizes of the binders can be found in Table 2 and Table 3,
 108 respectively.

109 *Table 1 – Mix composition by mass and water/binder (w/b) ratio. All formulations had a binder:aggregate*
 110 *ratio of 1:3 by volume.*

Binder composition	Total cement by mass (g)	Total metakaolin by mass (g)	Total lime by mass (g)	w/b (mass)
C100L0	289	0	0	0.7
C50L50	125	0	65	1.07
M33L67	0	28	86	1.91

111

112 *Table 2 - Chemical composition of each binder as provided by their respective manufacturers.*

Constituent	Cement	Metakaolin	Lime
CaO	66 %	7 - 11 %	> 80 %
MgO	0.8 %	0 - 5 %	< 5 %
CaO + MgO	-	-	> 90 %
SiO ₂	16 %	70 - 75 %	-
Na ₂ O	0.08 %	10 - 15 %	-

Al ₂ O ₃	4 %	0.5 - 5 %	-
SO ₃	2.5 %	-	< 2 %
K ₂ O	0.4 %	0 - 4 %	-
Fe ₂ O ₃	3 %	-	-
Cl ⁻	0.04 %	-	-
CO ₂	-	-	< 4
H ₂ O	-	-	< 2 %

113

114 *Table 3 – Particle size distribution by laser diffraction from binders tested.*

Material	d10		d50		d90	
	Average [μm]	COV [%]	Average [μm]	COV [%]	Average [μm]	COV [%]
CEM II-A/L 32.5R	1.7	1.9%	10.6	3.4%	34.3	2.6%
Metakaolin	3.0	3.4%	7.9	1.4%	16.8	0.9%
CL90S	2.5	0.9%	6.4	1.3%	16.7	2.2%

115

116 *1.1.2. Sample preparation*

117 The samples were designed by adapting Van Mullem et al. [21]’s active crack control and water
 118 permeability test to cylindrical samples. Nine samples per mortar composition were cast in 50 x 45 mm
 119 (height x diameter) PVC cylinders with one side sealed with epoxy resin. A cast-in-hole of 5 mm
 120 was created using a very well-oiled reinforcement bar that traverses the sample horizontally at the half (Figure
 121 1) which would be the inlet through which water would flow during the water permeability tests. Mortar
 122 mixes were prepared and cured in accordance with EN 1015-11 standard for masonry mortars.
 123 Accordingly, a double layer of gauze, 6 layers of filter paper and a 5 kg load were placed on the exposed
 124 surface of M33L67 samples, which exceed the 50 % lime content, for 3 h after casting.

125

126 *Figure 1 – Picture (A) and schematic drawing (B) of samples used in this study.*

127 Samples were cured for 2 days in the case for cement- or 5 days for metakaolin-containing mixtures (which
 128 showed slower hardening), at 95 % relative humidity (RH) and room temperature (RT) of 20 °C. Then, they

129 were demoulded, the reinforcement bar removed and left to cure further until 7 days of age at 95 % RH
130 and RT of 20 °C. At day 7, the first 10 mm of the cast-in-hole was enlarged to 6 mm diameter and plastic
131 tubing was inserted and glued. This tubing would be used to connect the samples to the water flow setup.
132 The opposite side of the cast-in-hole was sealed with silicone to prevent leakage. Samples were wrapped
133 in duct tape and split with a Brazilian splitting test to create a crack perpendicular to the cast-in-hole. The
134 duct tape ensured the two halves remained together and did not shift. To ensure the same sizes of cracks
135 in all specimens the crack width was adjusted using two plastic hose clamps to reach ~300 µm at the
136 widest part. The adjusted side was the top side of the sample where the crack mouth was located.
137 Aluminium tape was placed on the crack opening in the bottom side of the cylinder, which was not
138 studied, to ensure leakage during water flow tests occurred only through the exposed crack opening at
139 the top face. Epoxy was then used to cover the vertical crack openings on the circumference of the
140 cylinder to further ensure water tightness. The epoxy glue was left to dry for 24 h.

141 **1.2. Methods**

142 *1.1.1. Experimental workflow*

143 Three of the nine samples per mortar composition with the most similar crack widths were chosen. Crack
144 widths were first measured, and samples were placed under water for 24 h before testing water flow as
145 described below. After testing, the samples were left to dry for 24 h. The samples were then scanned with
146 micro-CT. After scanning, all samples were placed under water for 28 days to stimulate healing. Each
147 formulation was located in a different container and tap water was used in all cases. After 28 days the
148 samples were allowed to dry for 24 h and crack widths were measured again. The samples were then
149 scanned a second time with micro-CT. Lastly, samples were placed under water for 24 h before performing
150 a second round of water flow tests.

151 *1.1.2. Microscopy*

152 Crack widths at the crack mouth were measured using an optical microscope (Leica DMC 2900). Three
153 regions of interest (ROIs) free of irregularities on each crack were photographed and 30 measurements
154 per ROI were taken. The average width of the crack was calculated from the average width of each zone.

155 *1.1.3. Water flow tests*

156 Crack width measurements are a simple but effective way of showing the healing capacity of mortars at
157 the surface. Nonetheless, it does not provide insight into the durability of the precipitated healing
158 products. In this work, water permeability tests were chosen due to their non-destructive nature, in
159 particular water flow tests, which have short testing times and high accuracy [22].

160 Briefly, the mortar samples were submerged in water for 24 h prior to testing for water permeability. This
161 pre-treatment ensured no air remained in the sample which could affect the continuous flow of water
162 during the test. Afterwards, the cylindrical samples were gripped with a stand and clamp with the opening
163 side facing downwards at a height of 20 cm from a measuring scale. A hose connected the tubing on the
164 cylinder to a closed water reservoir 30 cm above. When the test started, the reservoir was opened and
165 water flowed from the reservoir through the tubing finally passing through the crack in the cylinder. The
166 flowing water was collected on a container placed on top of the measuring scale and the weight of water
167 was measured over time. Water was allowed to flow for 30 s prior to measuring to remove remaining
168 entrapped air and weight measurements were taken every 30 s for 5 minutes (10 times in total). After the
169 test, the samples were placed under water again to prevent air bubbles from being entrapped in the crack
170 until the sample was measured again. All samples were measured three times.

171 1.1.4. X-ray micro-computed tomography (micro-CT)

172 Three samples per formulation with a size of 50 x 45 mm (height x diameter) were scanned by micro-CT
173 at a voxel size of 30 μm (180 kV, 30 W, exposure time 750 ms) using the CoreTOM scanner (TESCAN) at
174 Ghent University's UGCT facilities. The samples were placed on a rotating stage between an X-ray source
175 and X-ray detector. The samples were scanned using a 1 mm aluminum filter, and 2783 projections were
176 obtained of a 360° scan of the cylindrical sample. The same acquisition and reconstruction parameters
177 were used for the scans before and after healing to allow comparison between scan dates. After scanning,
178 the scans were reconstructed using the Panthera 1.4.4 software by TESCAN XRE, and this yielded a
179 reconstructed volume with 1873 slices of 1855 x 1855 voxels. All scans can be found in the YODA
180 repository of Utrecht University (link under construction). Further volume analysis was performed on the
181 image analysis software Avizo 2020.3.

182 1.1.5. Volume analysis

183 After scanning and reconstructing the samples, Avizo 2020.3 was used to study the effects of healing on
184 the crack volume. First, the before (date 0) and after healing (date 28) 3D volumes were aligned, taking
185 the main crack as a reference for the resampling. Second, the segmentation of the pores in the before
186 and after healing volumes was performed using a manual thresholding segmentation process. A
187 conservative thresholding value was manually chosen that would best consider only the air voids based
188 on the histogram of the before and after healing volumes. An intensity range of 0-17171 (on 16-bit images)
189 was settled on and applied to scans from date 0 and 28 after confirming that both grey-scale histograms
190 did not change. Then, a cylindrical region of interest of 46.25 mm in diameter and 46.35 mm high was
191 selected to remove non-mortar information from the analysis. Morphological attributes were assigned to
192 each element, and the crack system was then isolated from the rest of the pores and air voids using a
193 filter analysis based on the 3D volume values (Figure 2). Given that the crack can be considered as a single
194 large pore, with a small maximum opening compared to its equivalent diameter and a large total volume,
195 it was easy to filter out as all air voids have a similar maximum opening and equivalent diameter and a
196 smaller total volume. This allowed us to simplify the volume analysis workflow, and only features above
197 the maximum resolution were accounted for. Then, the volume difference was calculated and regarded
198 as the effective crack healing of each sample.

199 Figure 2 – Simplified schematic representation of the image analysis workflow on a step-by-step basis. Top
200 shows a 2D cross section of the 3D volume represented below. From left to right: Raw data was
201

202 *reconstructed and rendered; air voids (including the crack) were segmented by manual thresholding; all*
 203 *air voids were labelled based on their 3D volume; all air voids smaller than the crack volume were filtered*
 204 *out. NB: The whole cylinder was used for the final analysis. Scale bar: 1.5 cm.*

205 The volume differences only provided a value of the volume change before and after healing. As such, in
 206 order to visualize and quantify the healing products, the reconstructed cracks at both ages were
 207 subtracted from each other. This yielded a greyscale image that represented the changes during
 208 submersion under water for 28 days, i.e. the healing products (Figure 3C, E). These changes could then be
 209 visualized in a 3D volume to observe where the precipitates had formed.

210
 211 *Figure 3 – 3D visualization of the reconstructed volume (A), with the crack volume at date 0 in yellow (B),*
 212 *the resulting healing products at date 28 in blue (C), and overlapped crack volume and healing products*
 213 *(D). Density map of the healing products highlighting the location of the of self-healing products by size*
 214 *(E). Scale bar: 1.5 cm.*

215 Finally, a slice fraction analysis was performed after acquiring the crack volume subtraction, whereby the
 216 fraction occupied by the healing products in each of the 1873 slices of the total scanned volume was
 217 calculated as:

218
$$\text{Slice fraction (\%)} = \frac{\sum \text{healing products}}{\text{Slice volume}} * 100,$$

219 where the slice volume is 56000 x 56000 x 30 μm (length x width x height).

220 **1.3. Healing efficiency coefficients**

221 In order to compare the different tests to each other all measurements were converted to healing
 222 efficiencies (HE).

223 The HE of crack widths (HE_w) tests was calculated as:

224
$$HE_w = \frac{\text{Crack width before healing} - \text{Crack width after healing}}{\text{Crack width before healing}} * 100$$

225 The HE of water flow tests (HE_q) was calculated as:

226
$$HE_q = \frac{\text{Average water flow rate before healing} - \text{Average water flow rate after healing}}{\text{Average water flow rate before healing}} * 100$$

228 The HE of the crack volume analysis (HE_v) was calculated as:

229
$$HE_v = \frac{\text{Crack volume before healing} - \text{Crack volume after healing}}{\text{Crack volume before healing} - \text{Volume of cast-in-hole}} * 100$$

230 The subtraction in the denominator of the last equation was a correction for the cast-in-hole. Due to the
 231 cast-in-hole having as big a volume (870 mm³) as the crack of most samples, the conversion to HE was
 232 skewed as this volume would never heal. For this, the mathematical correction was performed, namely
 233 subtracting the cast-in-hole volume from the crack volume, in order to account for this when converting
 234 to HE. To corroborate that the mathematical removal of the cast-in-hole was an accurate approximation
 235 applicable to all samples, three of the nine samples scanned with micro-CT had further image analysis
 236 steps to confirm the approximation accuracy, which can be found in the supplementary data. To compare
 237 significant differences of HE between groups a one way ANOVA test ($p = 0.05$) was performed on R.

238 **3. Results and Discussion**

239 **1.1. Sample requirements for coupled test**

240 The main limiting factor in the design of the samples was adjusting the size of the specimen to be
 241 representative for all the three tests coupled. Micro-CT scans require small specimens in order to achieve
 242 high resolutions. For example, Snoeck et al. [14] used small 10 x 6 mm³ (height x diameter) cylinders to
 243 reach a resolution of 6 μm while Kontiza et al. [17] chose prisms of 20 x 5 x 5 mm³ (length x width x
 244 thickness) to reach a voxel size of 9 μm. Such small samples were not possible in this case, given that for
 245 water permeability tests, the flow of water that goes through the sample is affected by the crack width
 246 [22]. For this, standard sized prisms with crack lengths of 40 mm are generally tested. Furthermore, the
 247 commonly chosen 300 μm crack width for self-healing tests, which is often beyond what autogenous
 248 healing can heal [3], would be non-representative in such small specimens. Finally, small cores are
 249 generally obtained through wet drilling or cutting, which is not desirable or not possible for softer binders
 250 such as the M33L67 mix tested in this work.

251 This meant that it was necessary to work with larger sized specimens. Few studies using micro-CT have
 252 looked at self-healing in larger samples. Zhang et al. [23] prepared specimens of 50 mm in diameter to
 253 achieve a resolution of 56 μm voxel size, yet their work was limited to qualitative assessments of the
 254 internal healing of the crack. Meanwhile, Van Stappen et al. [15] who were interested in looking at the
 255 release of healing agents into the sample, chose a 60 x 60 x 60 mm³ sample to visualize the capsules
 256 embedded in the matrix of the mortars, yet reached a voxel size of 46.3 μm. Nevertheless, the process of
 257 healing through polymers is observable at lower magnifications than those of autogenous healing, which
 258 meant that lower resolutions were sufficient. Interestingly, Fukuda et al. [20] performed SEM analysis up
 259 to a magnification of 1000x and micro-CT scans with voxel size of 16 x 16 x 25 μm (length x width x depth)

260 on the same area of study. Despite the resolution differences reached by both techniques, they showed
261 that there was a good correlation and agreement in terms of self-healing measurements at this resolution.

262 In the final sample design for this work (Figure 1), a balance was struck for a sample size of 45 mm in
263 diameter, with which a voxel size of 30 μm was achieved, close to the resolution achieved by Fukuda et
264 al. [20] who showed that a 25 μm voxel was good enough in resolution to show the onset of self-healing.
265 This size still allows for a large enough crack mouth for representative microscopy and water permeability
266 tests. Cylinders were chosen to maximize the effectiveness of the detector's surface and to reach the
267 highest resolution possible by closing the distance between the X-ray source and the sample stage. The
268 samples were cast with a rod to create a cast-in-hole for the adapted water flow tests. A Brazilian splitting
269 test was used to crack the specimen as this allows the creation of a single crack on a localized area of
270 study. Alternatively, it is possible to damage samples through compression, but this can lead to a more
271 complex and variable crack system [24]. Furthermore, compressive loading also creates several
272 microcracks which are known to have a large effect on the 3D volume healing [18]. Having a single crack
273 reduced the variables at the time of study. The maximum width of the crack was adjusted to $\sim 300 \mu\text{m}$
274 using a commercial plastic clamp on the cylindrical sample. The use of plastic was necessary as metal
275 which is more often used, would interfere with the X-rays.

276 **1.2. Crack width measurements**

277 The crack width was measured before and after healing to observe the progress of self-healing at the
278 surface of the samples. First, an average crack width of $\sim 300 \mu\text{m}$ was achieved for all 9 samples at date 0,
279 indicating that the plastic clamps were successful in adjusting the crack width. Nevertheless, a large
280 standard deviation was observed in the crack width (Figure 4) for each individual sample. This was due to
281 the Brazilian splitting method used to create the cracks which produces V-shaped cracks, which are wider
282 at one end of the crack mouth (Supplementary Figure 1). Despite the shape of the crack mouth, after the
283 healing period all samples showed a reduction in the crack width (Figure 4). A randomized block design
284 statistical analysis was performed to determine whether healing occurred to different extent depending
285 on the wider or narrower end of the crack. It was possible to isolate the crack location through a block
286 design in the statistical analysis, as the crack width was similar at each location between the samples
287 (Supplementary Figure 2). Naturally, the chosen location along the crack length (at the mouth) had an
288 effect on the healing efficiency due to the varying width (100 – 300 μm), with the wider sections across
289 all formulations showing very little healing. Still, the cracks were significantly different before and after
290 healing for all samples for $p < 0.05$.

291 The importance of crack width in the healing efficiency as demonstrated by the varying crack size of the
292 samples, stresses the limitations of previous micro-CT studies performed with smaller specimens. While
293 smaller cracks may have shown good healing, their results may not be representative of the results
294 obtained with other techniques that assess larger and more typical crack sizes. As such, these studies may
295 not offer a complete representation of the self-healing capacity of the studied materials, despite their
296 precision in depicting outcomes in smaller samples.

297

298 *Figure 4 – Average crack width for each sample of all three formulations at date 0 (grey bars) and date 28*
 299 *(yellow bars) after healing, with indication of the calculated HE_w. Three ROIs per sample were measured*
 300 *to calculate the average crack width and the standard error (error bars). * indicates non-significant healing*
 301 *for p < 0.05.*

302 Of the formulations tested, C100L0 had the best healing efficiency of cracks (HE_w) on average while
 303 M33L67 was the least effective. Regardless, the formulation had non-significant effect on the healing
 304 efficiency.

305 1.3. Change in water flow

306 Like the crack width measurements, the water flow test showed a significant reduction in flow for all
 307 samples ($p < 0.05$), indicating that the self-healing products were sound (Figure 5). Still, the extent of
 308 autogenous healing was rather limited. Analysis of the healing efficiency (HE_q) between formulations
 309 showed that M33L67 had a tendency to underperform in comparison with C50L50 and C100L0, despite
 310 that these differences were not significant ($p < 0.05$). This can be attributed to the differences in the self-
 311 healing products expected to have been formed. Considering that the samples were cracked at 7 days,
 312 the hydration reactions were still ongoing, while the fact that the samples were taken from 95 % RH to be
 313 submerged under water highly reduced the formation of carbonation products. This likely promoted the
 314 formation of hydration products in the cracks of cement containing formulations and pozzolanic reactions
 315 in the lime-metakaolin binder mix. The cement hydration proceeds faster than the pozzolanic reactions,
 316 explaining the better performance of the cement-containing mixtures [25]. Although, it was expected for
 317 precipitation of carbonation products in the lime-containing mixtures to be low, any formation would
 318 have likely happened through diffusion of CO₂ dissolved in the water (Eq.1) and reaction with free Ca²⁺
 319 from dissolved Ca(OH)₂ (Eq.2-3) [26]. The fact that diffusion occurred through water and not air would
 320 have made this process 10000 times slower, though [27]. Such a difference in diffusion rates is seen as a

321 barrier to CO₂ transfer to the reaction front in water-saturated pores, leading to a reduced formation of
322 carbonation self-healing products [27].

326 Besides the lower performance, M33L67 also had the most variation in HE_q. This variation might arise
327 from M67L33 samples' inherent lower tensile strength which can cause more tortuous and inconsistent
328 cracks when cracking. Previously, Edvardsen [26] proposed equation (Eq.4) to model water flow (*q*)
329 through a natural crack, and defined a reduction factor to adjust for the roughness of naturally occurring
330 cracks (ξ):

331
$$q = \frac{\xi \cdot \Delta p \cdot b \cdot w^3}{12\eta \cdot d} (Eq. 4)$$

332 where Δp is the differential water pressure between inlet and outlet of a crack (in N/m²), *w* is the width
333 of the crack (in m), η the absolute viscosity of the fluid passing through the crack (in Ns/m²) and *d* is the
334 thickness of the structure through which the water flows (in m). Following the same reasoning Van Mullem
335 et al. [22] applied to simplify the relation between *q* and *w*, it is possible to relate *q* to crack geometry, by
336 rewriting Eq. 4 as:

337
$$q = \xi \cdot A (Eq. 5)$$

338 where *A* is a constant, given that the setup used was the same for all samples, the samples had the same
339 dimensions and an average crack width was similar for all samples.

340

341 *Figure 5 – Water flow values obtained at date 0 (grey lines) and date 28 (yellow lines) after healing on all*
 342 *three formulations, with indication of the calculated HE_q. Measurements were performed in triplicates with*
 343 *a low percentage of variability.*

344 It is important to highlight that the water flow of the adapted samples showed an acceptably low
 345 variability (COV 0.01-0.04) between the three repetitions on the same samples before healing – a
 346 requirement by Van Mullem et al. [22] to ensure that the test was consistent and repeatable. This showed
 347 that it was possible to implement water flow tests in these adapted samples for micro-CT.

348 Overall, C100L0 showed the best HE_w and HE_q while M33L67 was the least effective, even though these
 349 differences were non-significant. In fact, there was a clear correlation between high HE_w and HE_q in all
 350 samples (r = 0.88) (Figure 6), which has been previously established with other water permeability tests
 351 and in concrete [27]. Despite the positive correlation between HE_w and HE_q, the magnitude of HE_w was
 352 larger than HE_q. The difference in magnitude was also seen in the work of Roig-Flores et al. [27] although
 353 not expanded upon. This difference could be explained due to the nature of the tests. Whereas
 354 microscopy measurements were limited to the three ROIs at the crack surface, water flow tests measure
 355 a phenomenon across length and height of the whole crack, encompassing surface and internal aspects
 356 as well as durability of the healing products. As such, unmeasured changes in the crack mouth could still
 357 have an impact on water flow tests. For example, it is possible that for the 2nd and 3rd C50L50 samples,
 358 with the same HE_q but different HE_w (Table 4), healing occurred to the same extent in the samples but the

359 specific ROIs chosen for crack width measurements or the depth of the formation of the products in each
 360 sample showed varying degree of healing.

361 The inability to firmly determine the cause of sample variability, likely due to whether the healing within
 362 the sample was as extensive as on the surface, illustrates that self-healing is a phenomenon influenced by
 363 multiple parameters that need to be measured in 3D to be able to fully characterize the system, as stated
 364 by Van Stappen et al. [15]. Therefore, the use of micro-CT offers a valuable insight into understanding how
 365 internal changes in the crack system lead to differences between changes in the crack width and water
 366 flow tests.

367 **1.4. Crack volume analysis using micro-CT**

368 The crack volume at date 0 and date 28 was extracted through volume analysis of the micro-CT scans and
 369 the progression of healing in the crack was calculated from the change in volume. Similarly to the two
 370 previous tests, no significant difference was observed for HE_v between formulations ($p < 0.05$). This time,
 371 no trend was present between formulations, either. All samples had a lower crack volume after the
 372 healing cycle, but the magnitude of the decrease differed, leading to a different HE_v, with two samples as
 373 outliers, namely the 3rd M33L67 sample which showed a 24 % decrease and the 2nd C100L0 sample which
 374 reduced by 16 % (Table 4). The rest of the samples showed limited healing.

375 *Table 4 – Summary table showing HE values (%) for all three tests on studied samples alongside average*
 376 *and standard deviation per formulation. * indicate samples analyzed in-depth using image analysis*
 377 *software.*

Formulation	Sample	HE _w	HE _q	HE _v
C100L0	1st*	40	26	3.7
	2nd	68	33	16
	3rd	41	17	2.6
	Average	50	25	7
	St. dev.	13	7	6
C50L50	1st	29	17	8.4
	2nd*	38	25	10
	3rd	58	25	1
	Average	42	22	6
	St. dev.	12	4	4
M33L67	1st*	28	8	24
	2nd	59	32	2.2
	3rd	20	6	4.6
	Average	36	15	10
	St. dev.	17	12	10

378

379 During the initial stages of the volume analysis two thresholding values, one more conservative (intensity
380 range 0-17171) than the other (0-20190), were used to perform crack volume calculations based on the
381 greyscale distribution in the histogram together with visual observations. Multiple thresholds were
382 chosen to explore which values returned the most reliable results. The lower threshold value was selected
383 for the image analysis of healing products, as they returned more conservative values and prevented
384 overestimation of quantitative measurements. This reduced the chances of highly skewed results due to
385 errors, such as considering the lighter greyscales allocated to the binder as part of the crack system along
386 the edges.

387 The HE_v of the crack volume as obtained by micro-CT shows no correlation with HE_w ($R = 0.02$) (Figure 6)
388 or HE_q ($R = 0.05$) (correlation between HE_v and HE_q in Supplementary Figure 3). This highlights the
389 considerable variability of internal crack healing of mortars. Furthermore, it indicates that healing is
390 happening at the crack opening, which is studied by microscopy and water flow tests, but it does not fully
391 represent the true healing occurring through the sample. As such, using limited testing methods might
392 not provide a robust understanding of the true effectiveness of self-healing agents or formulations when
393 studied in isolation. To our knowledge, the use of coupled techniques is a relatively uncommon approach
394 in the study of self-healing. One example of such work is from Fan and Li [18], who reported the
395 relationship between micro-CT volume differences with other tests using the same samples. It was
396 observed that resonance frequency and microscopy tests did not show good agreement with crack volume
397 changes. On the other hand, stiffness recovery showed almost direct association to crack volume changes.
398 These results are consistent with those reported by Sidiq et al. [16] who saw a correlation between HE_v
399 and compressive strength but not HE_w , although they performed each test on a different series of
400 samples. It should be stressed, even though crack width measurements are the go-to technique for
401 quantifying self-healing in most cases, they do not seem to provide a robust evaluation that is
402 representative for the entire crack system [2]. As such, we present a contribution towards the application
403 of more robust and comprehensive testing towards understanding self-healing in construction mortars.

404

405
 406 *Figure 6– Correlation of HE_q vs HE_w (A) and HE_v vs HE_w (B) with a linear regression model and the respective*
 407 *R^2 values. The red outlines indicate the samples analyzed in-depth using image analysis software.*
 408 *Correlation between HE_v and HE_q can be seen in Supplementary Figure 3.*

409 1.5. Self-healing products analysis using micro-CT

410 To further understand the internal changes occurring in the specimens, three of them were analyzed in
 411 depth by image analysis. This was limited to one specimen per formulation due to the time-consuming
 412 and resource-intensive nature of image analysis. Given that the samples were designed to be closer in size
 413 to standard specimens more often used in other studies, it is expected that the dynamics observed in the
 414 selected samples would be representative of self-healing, despite the expected heterogeneities that occur
 415 from sample to sample of a similar mixture. Crack width change, the most commonly measured parameter
 416 in self-healing, was taken as a reference for comparison between formulations. As such, three samples
 417 with similar HE_w from each formulation were studied further. The three selected samples (Table 4)
 418 covered the whole spectrum of the tested variables: the 2nd M33L67 sample showed large HE_v and low
 419 HE_q , the 3rd C100L0 sample showed moderate HE_q and low HE_v and the 2nd C50L50 sample had a higher
 420 HE_q and an intermediate HE_v (Figure 6).

421 For each sample, the self-healing products or precipitates were isolated through the differential volume
 422 obtained by the subtraction of the reconstructed crack volumes before and after healing. The fraction
 423 occupied by all healing products per slice of the reconstructed volumes was calculated using image
 424 analysis software (Avizo 2020.3). The analysis of the sizes of the slice fractions shows that the extent of
 425 healing in each sample was widely distributed (Figure 7). The lime-containing formulations had a bimodal
 426 size distribution of healing, with M33L67 having overall regions with less healing products than C50L50.

427 C50L50 also had a more rightwards skew towards regions with more healing than the other formulations.
 428 C100L0 had a normal distribution. Interestingly, the number of non-zero slice fractions was similar. This
 429 meant that major volume differences can be attributed to the overall size of the healing products at
 430 specific locations.

431
 432 *Figure 7 – Histogram (bin width 0.002) for the slice fractions larger than 0 of a representative sample per*
 433 *formulation. The slice fraction represents the percentage of healing products that occupy a single 30*
 434 *µm slice of the reconstructed volume, with slices taken perpendicular to the cylinder axis.*

435 The slice fraction was also used to identify the areas along the height of the crack where healing was most
 436 predominant (Figure 8). In M33L67 healing products were located at the top of the crack but not directly
 437 at the mouth. Meanwhile in C50L50, these were at the top, specifically at the mouth, and bottom, i.e. also
 438 at the sealed side of the crack. The presence of healing products at the top of the crack is likely due to the
 439 requirement of CO₂ and moisture ingress for the formation of precipitated healing products, and as these
 440 diffuse into the crack, they will first react with the unreacted material at the crack opening [28]. This has
 441 been extensively reported previously [18,20,23,29]. With regards to the rest of the crack, healing was
 442 consistent over its depth in all formulations. This has been reported for cracks of sufficient width (> 100
 443 µm), which allow faster transport of water allowing the formation of healing products deeper in the crack,
 444 mainly continued hydration of cement and pozzolanic reactions from metakaolin [18]. Overall, the
 445 concentration of healing products at the crack mouth also explains how reductions in water flow and crack
 446 width changes were reported and did not correlate to the overall volume decrease measured in the cracks
 447 of some samples.

448

449 *Figure 8 – Slice fraction analysis of a sample per formulation. The slice fraction represents the percentage*
 450 *of healing products that occupy a single 30 μm slice of the reconstructed volume, with slices taken*
 451 *perpendicular to the cylinder axis. The mean fraction of healing products for each sample is represented*
 452 *by the dotted line.*

453 On a side note, it is important to highlight that aforementioned works often do not reported how the
 454 samples were placed during healing, and it is not possible to know whether the formation of healing
 455 products is influenced by the positioning of the samples, or if it spontaneously occurs in this way. In this
 456 work, the samples were placed with the crack mouth facing downwards, and only M33L67 showed
 457 preference for the formation of healing products at the crack mouth. Therefore, the effect of positioning
 458 of samples during healing remains a debated topic and the positioning should be reported in the literature
 459 in order to reach more certain conclusions [30].

460 The slice fractions presented above only provide a 2D representation along the height of the crack of what
 461 was measured in 3D. Visualizing the healing in 3D (Figure 9) shows more accurately clusters of healing
 462 products rather than an even distribution along the length and height of the crack. This is clear for the
 463 C50L50 sample where there is a clustering of healing products at the bottom edges of the cylinder (Figure
 464 9). The healing at the top surface seemed better distributed along the length of the crack. On the other
 465 hand, C100L0 showed a more evenly distributed healing progress, as seen on the slice fraction analysis.

466
 467 *Figure 9 – Distribution of healing products through the whole crack. Clusters of healing are more visible as*
 468 *indicated by the heat map with red indicating where the larger healing products are and blue the smallest.*
 469 *Scale bar: 1 cm.*

470 Moreover, the influence of pores on the healing became apparent upon 3D analysis of the samples.
 471 Particularly, for M33L67 and C100L0 clusters of healing were observed in the bottom half of the samples
 472 (Figure 9). These were pores removed from the crack network due to the precipitation of self-healing
 473 products at the pore-crack interface. Figure 10 shows a slice of the crack volume studied where a pore
 474 (top green arrow) is observed in the crack system before (Figure 10A) and after self-healing (Figure 10B).
 475 The area of the crack before healing (Figure 10C, green plus white selection) includes this pore, whereas
 476 it is observed that the pore is no longer considered in the volume of the crack after healing (Figure 10C,
 477 green selection). This is due to self-healing products precipitating at the pore-crack interface connecting
 478 the isolated air void with the rest of the crack network. Areas where self-healing took place (blue arrows)
 479 are seen as light grey in the image compared to the darker areas without self-healing (green arrows) such
 480 as the pore itself (Figure 10B). Consequently, the crack system reduced in volume to a greater extent than
 481 the volume of the newly formed precipitates.

482
 483 *Figure 10 – 2D slice of a cracked mortar showing a pore (top green arrow) connected to the crack network*
 484 *before self-healing (A) and after self-healing (B). The healed area (C, white selection) considers both areas*
 485 *of precipitation (blue arrows) and no precipitation (green arrows), due to precipitation happening at the*
 486 *interface between the pore and the rest of the crack. Note that self-healing products are observed in B, as*

487 *the crack has a different grey value or lower attenuation coefficient than in A, the unhealed crack. Scale*
488 *bar: 2 mm.*

489 The change in crack volume has been used as a parameter to assess self-healing before [18]. Yet, the
490 phenomena of pores being blocked off by precipitation of self-healing products at the pore-crack interface
491 can cause a skew on the results on effective self-healing as the measured volume change of the crack
492 appeared to be larger than the actual precipitation of healing products. Interestingly, the influence of
493 pores has not been discussed in previous micro-CT studies even though micro-CT is an effective tool for
494 such work. Furthermore, this removal of pores could further influence the lack of correlation found
495 between HE_w and HE_v . A reduction in pores connected to the crack will have an impact on the crack
496 geometry, which has a strong influence on water permeability tests [22]. For example, it might lead to
497 more water flow as the crack becomes less tortuous and the water achieves more laminar flow. As such,
498 porosity could play an important undescribed effect on self-healing dynamics, particularly in water
499 permeability tests and needs to be further studied.

500 The influence of pore blocking on the final volumes used to calculate the HE_v raises the question on how
501 other dynamics can play a role when quantifying self-healing in micro-CT. Self-healing occurs by either the
502 reaction of unreacted binder particles or through the dissolution and reprecipitation of reacted hydration
503 and carbonation products. These dissolved products can reprecipitate in the crack or even leach from the
504 mortar matrix in the presence of water, leading to volume differences that cannot be attributed to healing
505 products. Although areas where the crack widened were visible in the scans, it is hard to attribute this
506 process to a specific phenomenon such as particle detachment or dissolution, especially when it is not
507 happening widely in the sample. Certain verifications can be made to confirm this, for example, Schröder
508 [31] confirmed dissolution was occurring in their samples because black regions (indicating deduction) in
509 the subtracted images were visible on both sides of the crack. In our case, the opposite phenomenon
510 occurs, where white regions were observed on both sides of the crack, and therefore, it was possible to
511 assign these changes to precipitation of healing products (Figure 11).

512 Furthermore, there is the possibility of detachment of mortar fractions from the crack wall, which can
513 either lead to expansion of the crack as well as mechanically blocking and healing of the crack [32]. Given
514 that all samples were handled in a similar manner this factor should be averaged out. Still, the different
515 binder strengths could mean that lower strength binders will undergo more influence of this
516 phenomenon. Only the movement of large particles in the crack were obvious in this work (Figure 11).

517

518 *Figure 11 – Dissolution and precipitation processes and shifting of particles visualized through micro-CT in*
 519 *a M33L67 sample. Changes in the crack geometry are observed before (A) and after (B) the healing period.*
 520 *The subtracted images (C-D) show in white those areas that appear in the crack after the healing period*
 521 *and in black those that disappear. White regions in C-D outlining the crack are a strong indication of*
 522 *precipitation while the shifting of a large particle is observed in black in the middle of the crack. Scale bar:*
 523 *2 mm.*

524 **4. Conclusion**

525 This work showed the importance of how coupled techniques are needed to better explain the
 526 phenomenon of self-healing, demonstrated here in lime-based mortars. We aimed at coupling three
 527 testing techniques: microscopic crack width measurements to study the progress of self-healing at the
 528 crack mouth, water flow tests for the assessment of durability of the self-healing products and micro-CT
 529 to understand the relation of the former two techniques to changes in the 3D volume of the crack in a
 530 non-destructive manner. The research highlights that microscopy and water permeability tests are not
 531 representing in a correct manner the effect of self-healing of an entire crack system. Healing was observed
 532 for all samples, albeit the autogenous healing was limited and no significant difference was observed
 533 between formulations. No correlation of HE_v was observed to HE_w or HE_q , highlighting that the results
 534 from HE_w and HE_q don't fully describe what is happening within the crack. This has not been reported
 535 before for water permeability tests and arose from healing occurring predominantly at the mouth of the
 536 crack. On the other hand, the HE_q was correlated to HE_w , although the magnitude of the two variables
 537 was different. Higher HE_w were observed than for HE_q , likely due to the microscopic evaluation being
 538 focused to certain regions of interest on the crack mouth while water flow tests quantify self-healing along
 539 the length and depth of the crack. Such a bias highlights the need of multiple testing techniques used
 540 simultaneously to more accurately describe the process of healing, while future research into self-healing
 541 should focus on validating these coupled techniques for other autonomous healing technologies. The
 542 choice of three different mortar compositions allowed to test the coupled techniques on materials with
 543 varying strength. Given that most research on self-healing is performed on cement-based materials, not
 544 all techniques are adaptable to all types of mortars (especially low strength mortars) [33].

545 Furthermore, studies of coupled techniques that assess two or more parameters in the same crack system
546 are limited and should become normalized as they are more robust, save time and numbers of samples.
547 Micro-CT offers an excellent opportunity to couple varying quantitative and descriptive techniques to
548 changes occurring throughout the crack system as shown here. The tortuosity of the crack seemed to have
549 an effect on the HE_q , with M33L67 being particularly affected by this given its lower strength. Another
550 potential influence on the tortuosity of the crack observed thanks to micro-CT scans, is related to the
551 pores connected to the crack. Qualitative analysis showed that pores were observed to have healed in the
552 volume analysis. Yet, it was shown that the pores did not show self-healing but had been removed from
553 the crack network through precipitation of healing products at the pore-crack interface. This meant the
554 measured volume change of the crack appeared to be larger than the actual precipitation of healing
555 products. Such a phenomenon has not been described previously. This can have an impact on the
556 tortuosity of the crack and as such affect water permeability tests as well. Nevertheless, more research is
557 needed combining both techniques.

558 At the same time, we worked towards a more representative study of self-healing by using samples that
559 were closer to standard-sizes, given most micro-CT research has focused on achieving high resolution and
560 has thus been applied on very small samples. In technical terms, micro-CT faces research constraints when
561 changes are happening beyond the resolution capacity of the scanners, which is limited by the minimum
562 representative size of the tested specimens. In this research, a compromise was made regarding a sample
563 size that would provide sufficient resolution for micro-CT and still allow to obtain representative results
564 for the other measurements by selecting standard-size specimens. The importance of larger samples was
565 highlighted with the observations made on smaller sections of the crack which always saw healing, while
566 wider regions did not. As such the use of small samples might not be showing representative healing
567 efficiencies of the studied materials as more healing would be expected due to the smaller crack sizes.
568 Nevertheless, for micro-CT studies it is often argued that small samples are needed to achieve good
569 resolutions, yet here it was shown how larger samples are possible without compromising on the
570 resolution needed to measure self-healing with micro-CT. The resolution may be insufficient to visualize
571 precisely what is happening only if studying micro-cracks. As such, the authors recommend to use even
572 larger samples that are more representative in future studies.

573 Nonetheless, micro-CT is not without flaws. Its computational demands and time-consuming analysis can
574 be challenging, while its learning curve is steep for initiating users. Furthermore, as the analysis process
575 involves the use of image analysis software, the workflow becomes user-dependent, for instance, on the
576 choice of a particular segmentation threshold which was a consideration made in this work. Although
577 certain quality checks can be performed, such as choosing more conservative thresholding values, it is
578 necessary to keep the operator bias in mind.

579 Lastly, to our knowledge, this is the first time that self-healing in lime-based mortars is reported for the
580 whole crack and that the use of micro-CT is reported for such formulations. Overall, work in lime-based
581 binders remains very limited, although there has been a recent rise in interest in alternatives to cement-
582 containing mortars. Nevertheless, many research techniques in the area of self-healing have been
583 developed for cement mortars which have higher strength and are not adapted for low-strength binders
584 [33], such as the M33L67 used in this work. This work also shows the potential of micro-CT as a feasible
585 technique to study self-healing in these materials.

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594 6. CRediT author statement

595 **Franco Grosso Giordano:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Formal Analysis, Investigation, Writing –
596 Original Draft. **Dulce Valdez Madrid:** Methodology, Software, Data Curation. **Laurenz Schröer:**
597 Investigation. **Nico Boon:** Funding acquisition. **Veerle Cnudde:** Writing – Review & Edition, Supervision.
598 **Nele De Belie:** Funding acquisition, Writing – Review & Edition, Supervision.

599 7. Supplementary Data

600 1.1. Correction for cast-in-hole in HE_v

601 In order to determine if the mathematically estimated volume of the cast-in-hole was correct, three
602 samples were analyzed further using image analysis software. For this, a mask of the same volume as the
603 cast-in-hole was manually created in the software. This mask was then used to selectively remove only
604 the cast-in-hole from all subsequent calculations of the crack volume. An increasing difference in
605 calculated HE_v was observed between the mathematical correction and the correction by masking as the
606 HE_v increased (Supplementary Table 1). Nonetheless, the error was considered acceptable.

607 *Supplementary Table 1 - Volume of the cracks at date 0 and date 28 adjusted for the volume of the cast-*
608 *in-hole by a mathematical operation or by masking operation.*

	Crack volume date 0 (cm³)	Crack volume date 28 (cm³)	Difference in crack volume (cm³)	HE_v with volume removed through mathematical operation (%)	HE_v with volume removed through masking operation (%)
C100L0	960	938	22	2.3	2.0
M33L67	848	668	180	21.2	25.5
C50L50	654	596	57	8.8	10.6

609

610 **1.2. Additional information on crack width measurements**

611
 612 *Supplementary Figure 1 – Three regions of interest (ROIs) free of irregularities that were photographed*
 613 *and measured on a C100L0 sample to calculate the average crack width. Due to the V-shape nature of the*
 614 *crack the crack gets progressively narrower along its length. The schematic (right) shows where on the*
 615 *crack these ROIs would be found. Scale bars, 500 μ m.*

616
 617 *Supplementary Figure 2 – Crack width at Bottom, Mid or Top locations along the length of the crack for*
 618 *each sample of all three formulations at date 0 (grey) and date 28 (yellow) after healing.*

619 **1.3. Additional information on crack volume analysis**

620
621 *Supplementary Figure 3 - Correlation of HE_v vs HE_q with the respective R^2 value. The red outlines indicate*
622 *the samples analyzed in-depth using image analysis software.*

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